

OVERVIEW OF PROJECTS, INITIATIVES, EVENTS AND PUBLICATIONS 2002-2025

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ABIS EU-FUNDED PROJECTS

- **Exploring Plausible Circular Futures - ExPliCiT (2023-2025)**

- While there is common agreement that the transition towards a Circular Economy (CE) could foster more sustainable futures, there is a lack of discussion about how a viable, feasible, and desirable CE system should be organised. Most of the current literature fails to recognise this, presenting the CE transition as a straightforward, neutral, and apolitical process, implicitly characterised by a techno-optimistic and eco-modernist stance. Most CE work is conducted at practical and technical levels, looking at material and energy flows. The basic assumptions concerning societal structures, along with underlying worldviews which should be embedded in a CE are largely overlooked or unclear. The project aims to bridge this gap through theoretical and practical research happening through academia-industry staff exchanges involving 5 academic and 5 non-academic partners.
- Website: <http://explicit-se.net/>
- Funding received: EUR 350,000
- Consortium partners: *Università degli Studi di Napoli Parthenope (coordinator), University of Vigo, Università Degli Studi di Catania, University of Sevilla, ABIS, University of Sheffield, FAEL - Federación Andaluza de Electrodomésticos y Otros Equipamientos del Hogar, CNA Campania Nord, Federconsumatori, Revertia.*

- **Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment (2023-2025)**

- Aiming to improve research careers and reduce career precarity, the project developed coordination and support measures to establish, test and implement a common Research Career Framework (RCF), which offered a structured and supportive skills and development model for researcher recruitment, employment, training, career progression and mobility. The RCF aimed to ensure career development and progression structure, recognise research and transferable skills and competencies, facilitate intersectoral collaboration and mobility, and deliver solutions against precariousness of research careers in academia.
- Website: <https://secureproject.eu/>
- Funding received: EUR 1 320 000
- Consortium partners: *PLOCAN - Oceanic Platform of the Canary Islands (coordinator), ABIS, CRAC - VITAE - Careers Research & Advisory Centre, Technopolis Group, ICoRSA - International Consortium of Research Staff Associations, EURODOC - European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers, MCAA - Marie Curie Alumni Association, Adoc Talent Management, YERUN - Young European Research Universities Network, University of Rijeka, University of Cyprus, Nova University Lisbon, UEFISCDI - Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding, Austrian Institute of Economic Research, CPN - Center for the Promotion of Science, WIFO, VDI/VDE Innovation.*

- **Open Universal Science – OPUS (2023-2025)**

- The OPUS project developed coordination and support measures to reform the assessment of research and researchers at Research Performing Organisations and Research Funding Organisations towards a system that incentivises and rewards researchers to take up Open Science practices. With a specific focus on reforming the research(ers) assessment system, the consortium conducted a comprehensive state of the art on literature and initiatives for open science, designed a set of interventions, developed and tested indicators and metrics to monitor and drive open science, and utilised stakeholder-driven feedback to refine and validate actions. The outcomes of the project were also synthesized into policy briefs.
- Website: <https://opusproject.eu/>
- Funding received: EUR 1 727 000
- Consortium partners: *PLOCAN - Oceanic Platform of the Canary Islands (coordinator), CRAC - VITAE - Careers Research & Advisory Centre, Technopolis Group, ICoRSA - International Consortium of Research Staff Associations, ABIS, EURODOC - European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers, Jisc, MCAA - Marie Curie Alumni Association, Research Council of Lithuania, RESOLVO, University of Rijeka, University of Cyprus, Nova University Lisbon, University of Vilnius, UEFISCDI - Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding, UNESCO - United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization, Trustinside, YERUN - Young European Research Universities Network.*

- **Realising the Transition to the Circular Economy (2018-2023)**

- ReTraCE was a research project under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative Training Networks funding scheme, that provided multidisciplinary training to 15 early-stage researchers (ESRs) on the transition towards a more sustainable mode of production and consumption in Europe. The researchers facilitated the implementation of the Circular Economy Strategy of the European Commission. The project provided policy insights and enhanced the understanding of the applicability of the CE paradigm from economic, environmental and social aspects.
- Website: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/814247>
- Funding received: EUR 4,040,000
- Consortium partners: *University of Sheffield (coordinator), Università Degli Studi di Napoli Parthenope, University of Kassel, South-East European Research Centre (SEERC), Dalarna University, TATA Steel UK, Olympia Electronics; ABIS Members involved: ABIS, Erasmus University Rotterdam, University of Kent.*

- **Harmonization and implementation of CSR EU Directives (2016-2018)**

- Within the Erasmus+ programme, ABIS participated as a project partner in the first EU project oriented at the examination of the success of the EU Directives in the areas of Corporate Social Responsibility. The main objective of this project was adult education and the exchange of examples of good practice between projects partners in this area.
- Website: www.hi4csr.com/en/about-project/

- Funding received: EUR 80,000
- Consortium partners: RRiF Group (coordinator), The Croatian Institute for CSR (IDOP), LUM Jean Monnet University, Ekvilib Institute, Bridging to the Future, Pontis Foundation, Global Impact Grid (GIG); ABIS

• Innovation for Sustainability (2013-2017)

- The I4S project was a research initiative that provided training and funding for researchers to investigate sustainability-driven innovation in business. One of the main outcomes of this project were various policy briefs that helped academics, practitioners and policy makers to foster sustainable innovation in doctoral training as well as the creation of new business models and to help implement measures that integrate sustainability at all education levels.
- Website: http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/106853_en.html
- Funding received: EUR 2,613,000
- Members involved: *ABIS, Copenhagen Business School, University of Exeter Business School, Alliance Manchester Business School, Rotterdam School of Management, Nyenrode Business University, Vlerick Business School, Leuphana Universität Lüneburg, University of Cape Town.*

• EU-InnovatE (2014-2017)

- EU-InnovatE was ABIS' largest EU project, which investigated the innovative and entrepreneurial roles of end users to shape a green and sustainable EU economy. In retrospect, the project helped to promote sustainable development-oriented policies that support the creation of jobs and to foster sustainable entrepreneurship in Europe for more sustainable innovation and financing.
- Website: http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/111217_en.html
- Funding received: EUR 4,770,000
- Members involved: *Technische Universität München, Aalto University, Aarhus University, ABIS, Kozminski University, Copenhagen Business School, Cranfield University, Forum for the Future, Katholische Universität Eichstätt- Ingolstadt, Politecnico di Milano, Technische Universiteit Eindhoven, Universidad de Navarra, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, Universiteit van Amsterdam.*

• CSR Impact (2010-2013)

- The European Commission's largest ever research and knowledge development initiative on CSR, supported by € 2.6 million in funding under the EU's 7th Framework Programme for Research. It was the first systematic attempt to measure the contribution of CSR to the social, economic and environmental goals of the European Union.
- Website: http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/95940_en.html
- Funding received: EUR 2,600,000
- Members involved: *ABIS, Central European University, Copenhagen Business School, INSEAD, IESE, Kozminski University, Politecnico di Milano, Tilburg University, University of Nottingham, WU Wien, Vlerick Business School.*

- **Business Case for Diversity (2007-2008)**

- The aim of the project was to place diversity management firmly on the strategic business agenda and activities of European companies of all sizes by encouraging the exchange of good practices and promoting the development of diversity policies and activities by businesses, employers and business schools
- Website: <http://www.iegd.org/pdf/Task%201-%20EBTP.pdf>
- Funding received: EUR 1,000,000
- Members involved: *ABIS, CSR Europe, EFMD.*

- **CSR Platform (2004-2007)**

- As project leader for CSR Platform, we helped to build the foundations for a European Research Area in the field and a European and Global reference point for the advancement and dissemination of knowledge on CSR by strengthening and expanding collaboration between academics between disciplines, between types of research (fundamental and applied research), between generations, and between the academic community at large and the business and other stakeholder communities.
- Website: http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/93062_en.html
- Funding received: EUR 750,000
- Members involved: *ABIS, EFMD, Ashridge Business School, Copenhagen Business School, Cranfield University, Leiden University, Vlerick Business School, The University of Warwick, The Copenhagen Centre, CSR Europe, Kozminski University, SGH Warsaw School of Economics, Katholische Universitaet Eichstatt-Ingolstadt, INSEAD.*

- **RESPONSE Project (2004-2006)**

- EU-funded project which was the world's largest research project on corporate responsibility and strategic stakeholder management and the network's flagship research initiative, which apart from the EU grant also received funds by ABIS' corporate founding partners - IBM, Johnson & Johnson, Microsoft, Shell and Unilever.
- Website: http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/74913_en.html
- Funding received: EUR 1,100,000
- Members involved: *ABIS, INSEAD, Copenhagen Business School, Kozminski University, SDA Bocconi School of Management, Kozminski University.*

ABIS PROJECTS AND OPINION LEADERSHIP INITIATIVES

- **Futures of Business Education in 2055 (2022-2024)**
 - In May 2022, ABIS launched a scenario building project to understand how the system of business education could change over the next 30 years. Aligned with its mission, the aim was to offer original, novel insights and solutions to foster pedagogical innovation and dialogue around management theory as well as institutional transformation in business education. Four alternative scenarios were built upon extensive research and stakeholder intelligence. The scenarios vary considerably and provide starting points for reflection and the development of responsive and adaptive strategies and policies. A final report was published in 2024 and is available at <https://zenodo.org/records/11477656>
- **Mentoring Programme for Early-Stage Researchers (2021-2024)**
 - The programme aimed to strengthen the learning and development of Early-Stage Researchers (ESRs) and to create supportive connections that are necessary to contribute to address current environmental and social challenges. The core of the programme, that ran each year from October to June, were one-to-one mentoring sessions for ESRs with experienced academics and business professionals in sustainability helping ESRs progress in their careers and make an impact on society. Regular workshops and meetings organized by ABIS were included. 24 mentor-mentee couples took part in the programme over the years. For more information, please refer to: www.abis-global.org/blog/mentoring-programme-for-early-stage-researchers
- **ABIS Sustainability Assessment (2020- 2024)**
 - ABIS designed and developed Sustainability Assessment is a management model to integrate sustainability in higher education institutions (HEIs), with the purpose to report to their decisionmakers:
 - The actual status of sustainability implementation at institutional and academic level
 - How to effectively enable sustainability initiatives
 - The impact of sustainability actions on the institution's stakeholders
 - Suggestions for priorities in developing sustainability strategies
 - ABIS members such as Nottingham Trent Business School and ESMT Berlin have undergone full assessment, with insights integrated into their sustainability strategy. For more information: www.abis-global.org/blog/abis-sustainability-assessment

- **Sustainable Investing Summer Course (2020-2022)**
 - ABIS co-organized three editions of the NN Investment Partners' Sustainable Investing Summer Course. First created in response to the COVID-19 pandemic, this opinion leadership initiative targeted the finance and asset management communities. 22 leading academics from the ABIS network and beyond shared their knowledge in lectures on key sustainability trends impacting the decisions of governments, companies as well as asset owners and investors. The initiative qualified for continuing education credits by the CFA Institute. More information can be found at: www.abis-global.org/blog/nn-investment-partners-sustainable-investing-summer-course-on-tour-2022-edition
- **Scenario Exploration System (2017 – 2024)**
 - The Scenario Exploration System (SES) is a serious gaming tool developed to facilitate the application of foresight in practice and designed to help participants, in less than 3 hours, to engage in systemic thinking with a long-term perspective and to explore alternative futures on specific issues. Over 7 years, ABIS pioneered the use of the SES in responsible management education and made significant contributions to its development. ABIS organized and facilitated over 30 SES workshops for HEIs, public organizations and NGOs across 12 countries. Over 600 participants, including university students, academic faculty members, policymakers, business and civil society representatives attended our workshops. Most recently, to meet increasing demand and geographic accessibility, ABIS developed SES facilitation trainings and trained 70 independent facilitators. More information is available at:
 - www.abis-global.org/blog/scenario-exploration-system-workshops
 - <https://zenodo.org/records/14724399>
- **Building Leaders for Long-Term Business Performance (2017)**
 - The project was an ambitious inquiry developed in 2017 by the University of Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership (CISL) in partnership with ABIS. It aimed to deepen the understanding of how multinational companies defined and developed their leadership and talent pipelines in order to thrive in an increasingly complex business environment, while simultaneously contributing to long-term social, environmental and economic goals. The project's research finding and outcomes were published in a final report available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/14718216>
- **The Future Board – An ABIS-Mazars Initiative (2016-2017)**
 - In autumn 2016, ABIS and Mazars organised two high-level roundtables to explore the stewardship role to be played by Boards of Directors in creating long-term, sustainable corporate success. These considered the macro trends and challenges that businesses are facing from different strategic, governance and leadership perspectives, as well as the innovation prospects for business schools in terms of research, executive development programmes, post-graduate curricula and wider corporate engagement. Website: www.abis-global.org/projects/the-future-board-an-abis-mazars-initiative

- **Global Talent Development Forum (2015-2016)**

- ABIS convened three high level dialogues convened by ABIS between December 2015 and October 2016, with invaluable support from founding partners Unilever and IBM. Through in-depth critical debate and reflection with senior HR, Leadership and Talent executives, we have sought to better understand the challenges facing business in trying to anticipate the various skills, qualities, mindsets and values that they believe will underpin both a sustainable, profitable business model and a long-term license to operate in an unprecedented VUCA world. For more information, please refer to: <https://www.abis-global.org/projects/abis-global-talent-forum>

- **The European Pact for Youth (2016-2017)**

- The Pact for Youth was a mutual engagement of business and European Union leaders. Initiated by CSR Europe, it brings together representatives for business, education and youth, and the European institutions. More information is available at: <http://www.csreurope.org/pactforyouth>

- **ABIS Education Initiative (2016)**

- In 2016, ABIS launched a Global Education Initiative to support the realization of its mission. The overall objective was to map and estimate members' Sustainable, Responsible and Ethical SRE educational offer. The findings were published in the resulting report, which is available under the ABIS Publications section.

- **Health as an Asset (2010 – 2016)**

- The Health as an Asset project, which was led by Rutgers University and the Johnson & Johnson Corporate Citizenship Trust contributed greatly to the third SDG. It created an international platform for experts drawing their expertise, passion and commitment from across the global spectrum - corporate, academic, donors, public policy and others - and all regions of the world, to meet in different “thinking spaces”, under Chatham House rules, for a “voyage of discovery” which helped identify decision making concepts, models and processes that lead to better health outcomes for all.

- **Managing the Responsible Business Challenge in Africa: an IBM-ABIS Strategic Programme (2014 – 2019)**

- A corporate-academic partnership programme, where ABIS partnered with various business schools in Africa to facilitate - together with the help of Unilever, GSK and IBM - greater collaboration between Africa' higher education institutions and business to address sustainability challenges. Please find more information at: <https://www.abis-global.org/projects/responsible-business-challenge-africa>

- **United Nations Global Compact LEAD Initiative (2011 – 2013)**
 - To challenge and support leading companies in reaching higher levels of corporate sustainability performance, Global Compact LEAD was launched in January 2011 as a leadership platform within the Global Compact.

- **Transforming Business-Government Relations For Competitiveness & Growth (2011-2012)**
 - In 2011, ABIS launched a qualitative, interview-based research with EPPA to examine how corporate leaders and senior policy figures perceive the influence of their interrelations on strategic decision-making. A select group of multinational companies across multiple sectors and EU institutions were engaged through interviews to explore how executives receive and internalize political signals, especially from the EU, and align regulatory risk / opportunity with business strategy and planning.

- **Practical Wisdom for Sustainable Management (2009-2014)**
 - This project aimed at overcoming the often-decried normative void in management education. As an outcome of this project, new approaches towards spiritual traditions were promoted, awareness was raised nationally and internationally, blog and press resonance, several MA theses and PhD projects realized and projected. Additionally, several special issues were launched addressing the various themes covered by the project.

- **Sustainable Value (2007-2009)**
 - *Sustainable Value: Corporate Responsibility, Market Valuation and Measuring the Financial and Non-Financial Performance of the Firm* was a two-year EABIS funded research project. Its purpose was to explore how the environmental, social and governance performance of companies might impact on the drivers of business success; how companies explain these linkages to investors, and how the investment community treats these data.

- **Managing Stakeholder Media (2007-2010)**
 - This project mapped and quantified the dynamics of “stakeholder” information media and their impacts on business, at a moment when these media platforms are supplanting news media as key vectors of opinion and action. The goal was to validate hypotheses of predictive value for business communication in CSR initiatives.

- **Principles for Responsible Management Education (2007-ongoing)**
 - As a co-creator of PRME and as a member of its Steering Committee, ABIS was part of the group of global and regional associations which advised the PRME Secretariat on a wide range of strategic and operational issues. Find more information at: <http://www.unprme.org/>.

ABIS EVENTS

ANNUAL COLLOQUIA

- 22nd Colloquium 2023: Navigating multiple transitions (Kozminski University, Warsaw & online)
- 21st Colloquium 2022: Business Principles for the Stakeholder Capitalism Era (ABIS, Brussels & online)
- 20th Colloquium 2021: Driving impact through responsible investing (online)
- 19th Colloquium 2020: Coming full circle - sustainability and future-proof global recovery (online)
- 18th Colloquium 2019: Business in Society - Measuring Impact and Creating Change (ESMT Berlin, Berlin)
- 17th Colloquium 2018: Sustainability as a Business Opportunity (Solvay, Brussels)
- 16th Colloquium 2017: Business-Academic Partnerships for the UN SDGs (ABIS, Brussels)
- 15th Colloquium 2016: Time for a Change and a new Agenda in Education, Learning & Talent Development (ABIS, Brussels)
- 14th Colloquium 2015: Global Sustainability Strategy: New models and approaches to achieve sustainable living (SDA Bocconi, Milan)
- 13th Colloquium 2014: Transforming Tomorrow: Leadership for a Sustainable Future (University of Cambridge, Cambridge)
- 12th Colloquium 2013: Sustainability & Finance (Nyenrode Business University, Breukelen)
- 11th Colloquium 2012: Strategic Innovation for Sustainability (IMD, Lausanne)
- 10th Colloquium 2011: The Changing Role of Business in Developing Countries (INSEAD, Fontainebleau)
- 9th Annual Colloquium 2010: Corporate Responsibility and Emerging Markets (Graduate School of Management, St. Petersburg State University, St. Petersburg)
- 8th Colloquium: 2009: The Role and Purpose of Business in Society: Challenges and Issues for Global and Corporate Governance (IESE, Barcelona)
- 7th Colloquium: 2008: Corporate Responsibility & Sustainability. Leadership and Organizational Change: Contextual and dynamic perspectives (Cranfield School of Management, Cranfield)
- 6th Colloquium 2007: The Emerging Global Governance Paradigm: The Role of Business and Its Implications for Companies, Stakeholders and Society (ESADE, Barcelona)
- 5th Colloquium 2006: Corporate Sustainability, Strategic Management and the Stakeholder View of the Firm (SDA Bocconi, Milan)
- 4th Colloquium 2005: Corporate Social Responsibility and Competitiveness (Kozminski University, Warsaw)

- 3rd Colloquium 2004: Corporate Social Responsibility and Responding to Societal Expectations (Vlerick Business School, Brussels)
- 2nd Colloquium 2003: Corporate Social Responsibility and Stakeholder Management (Copenhagen Business School, Copenhagen)
- 1st Colloquium 2002: CSR: A Blueprint for Business-Relevant Research (INSEAD, Fontainebleau)

KNOWLEDGE INTO ACTION FORA

- 8th Knowledge Into Action Festival 2022: Futures of Business Education (Brussels & online)
- 7th Knowledge Into Action Festival 2021 (online)
- 6th Knowledge Into Action Forum 2020: Towards a Circular Economy in Business and Education (online)
- 5th Knowledge Into Action Forum 2019: Driving Sustainable Innovation to Deliver Impact (Unilever, Kingston upon Thames)
- 4th Knowledge Into Action Forum 2018: Business Model Innovation in the SDG Era (ING, Brussels)
- 3rd Knowledge Into Action Forum 2017 (Brussels)
- 2nd Knowledge Into Action Forum 2016 (Brussels)
- 1st Knowledge Into Action Forum 2015 (Brussels)

OTHER EVENTS

- Biodiversity-Respectful Leadership Summer School (2024)
 - In collaboration with the University of Turku, ABIS organized a summer webinar series designed for business practitioners keen to explore biodiversity-related risks and opportunities. The series included 6 webinars with 14 speakers,
- Exploring foresight scenarios for the EU bioeconomy (2022-2023)
 - In 2022 and 2023, the European Commission's Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy organised three workshops to explore bioeconomy foresight scenarios. Thanks to the support and facilitation provided by ABIS, the workshops utilized the Scenario Exploration System (SES) to involve several stakeholders in the development of forward-looking thinking and policies for bioeconomy. Outcomes and insights can be found in the final report available at: <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC135536>
- Exploring sustainable futures with serious gaming (2021)
 - The event aimed to discuss the importance of foresight, systemic thinking and the main learnings and benefits of the Scenario Exploration System (SES). It brought together the original designers of the tool alongside many users who continue to apply the SES in academia, business and policy.

- ABIS-AMS Value Creation Roundtables (2020-2021)
 - ABIS and Antwerp Management School organized two ambitious roundtables as an exchange of knowledge, competences and ideas on sustainable transformation. Leading academics such as Mark Kramer, Stuart Hart, Robert Phillips, Jed Emerson, and Wayne Visser participated, together with representatives from EY, PwC, Johnson and Johnson, ABN AMRO, Port of Antwerp, Impact Institute and the Value Balancing Alliance. The resulting white paper and report are listed under the ABIS publications section.
- Horizon Europe Funding Webinar Series (2020-2021)
 - In 2020-2021 ABIS organized an ad-hoc webinar series on Horizon Europe, the EU's key funding programme for Research and Innovation for the years 2021-2027. The series featured speakers from the European Commission and META Group
- Webinar series 2019
 - As a follow up the ABIS Colloquium in 2018, in the following year ABIS organized a webinar series diving deeper into circular economy, sustainable finance and digitalization featuring 6 experts from IBM, Unilever, Alliance Manchester Business School and University of Exeter.
- Webinar series 2017
 - In 2017, ABIS hosted a series of 6 webinars on a wide range of topics related to sustainability and corporate responsibility with experts from GSK, Telanto, IESE, Copenhagen Business School, University of Amsterdam Business School, and Fresenius Business School.
- Doctoral Summer Schools (2013-2016)
- ABIS Thought Leadership Roundtable Series (2014)
- Best Practice Ethics Management Workshop
- Wisdom at Work Conference
- Innovation in teaching - a Brazilian/European learning journey
- Entrepreneurship & Sustainability Conference in Brazil
- ABIS Leaders Forum
- Experiential Learning Congresses

ABIS PUBLICATIONS

BOOKS

- Lenssen, G.G. & Smith, N. C. (Eds.), 2019, *Managing Sustainable Business - An Executive Education Case and Textbook*, Springer
 - This book provides a framework for managers to pursue sustainable business in a strategic way. At the same time, it is a learning model, starting with foundation risk management and stakeholder management and moving on to the more complex challenges of strategic differentiation and business model innovation.

- Lenssen, G.G., Rhee, J.H. & Martinez. F., 2016, *The Role of Corporate Sustainability in Asian Development*, Springer
 - Examines the antecedents, processes/operations and outcomes of corporate responsiveness to environmental and social issues in the context of Asia

- Smith, N. C. & Lenssen, G.G. (Eds.), 2010, *Mainstreaming Corporate Responsibility*, Wiley
 - The book pioneers a way for business schools to equip future business leaders and managers with the knowledge, skills and competencies to meet the current business challenges. Based upon a major curriculum development project run by the INSEAD Social Innovation Centre, London Business School and EABIS, this book is a collection of texts and cases for use in both core and specialized courses across business disciplines, including strategy, accounting, entrepreneurship, marketing, operations, and finance.

- Sachs, S., Rühli, E., & Kern, I., 2009. *Sustainable Success with Stakeholders: The Untapped Potential*. London: Palgrave Macmillan
 - This book shows managers how they can identify their stakeholders and cooperate with them in a mutually successful and satisfying way. It includes numerous examples from the case studies and from international firms, illustrating the stepping stones to a comprehensive stakeholder management.

- Ionescu-Somers, A. & Steger, U., 2009, *Business Logic for Sustainability: A Food and Beverage Industry Perspective*, Palgrave Macmillan
 - The food and beverage industry is vital to the global economy, but in a society increasingly concerned with sustainable development, it is facing new challenges. This book presents the results of a research project focused on the management challenges that sustainable development presents to food and beverage companies.

- Pinkse J. & Kolk, A., 2008, *International Business and Global Climate Change*, London: Routledge
 - This book provides a comprehensive analysis of international business responses to global climate change and climate change policy. Gives a concise treatment of developments in policy and business activity on global, regional and national levels, using examples and systematic data from a large number of international companies.

- Steger, U., Ionescu-Somers, A., Salzmann, O. & Mansourian, S., 2008, *Sustainability Partnerships. The Manager's Handbook*, Palgrave Macmillan
 - Social and environmental issues can be very complex and overwhelming for managers. A partnership seems like an obvious solution. But what type of partnership is appropriate, what are the pitfalls and how can they be overcome? The authors use the experiences of a number of experts in companies, NGOs and governmental bodies to find the answers.

- Kakabadse A., & Morsing, M. (Eds.), 2006, *Corporate Social Responsibility: Reconciling Aspiration with Application*, Palgrave Macmillan;
 - The book examines the challenges of regulating and reporting CSR application, exploring issues concerning all agencies involved. Recommendations for performance enhancement are complimented by insightful enterprise and case studies on CSR sustainability.

- Steger, U. (Ed.), 2006, *Inside the Mind of the Stakeholder: The Hype Behind Stakeholder Pressure*, Palgrave Macmillan
 - Evidence obtained from stakeholder groups in Europe is sobering indeed in the context of globalization and the constant striving for competitiveness. This book provides an honest and in-depth analysis of how stakeholders themselves assess and influence corporate sustainability.

- Kakabadse A., & Kakabadse N. (Eds.), 2006, *CSR in Practice: Delving Deep*, Palgrave Macmillan
 - This book delves deep into the application of corporate social responsibility, surfacing an uncomfortable reality. Honest intent without managerial skill results in CSR paucity. Studying insider trading, private healthcare and investment banking provision, it reflects an absence of ethical leadership, undermining corporate reputation.

- Steger, U. (Ed.), 2004, *The Business of Sustainability: Building industry cases for corporate sustainability*, Palgrave Macmillan
 - This book goes further than ever before in trying to be more specific about the economic rationale for corporate sustainability, by approaching this issue on an industry-specific level. To do this, empirical evidence was gathered from managers in nine industries, along with their stakeholders, during an extensive and ambitious research project.

ABIS SPECIAL ISSUES & PAPERS

- Corporate Governance Special Issue: Vol. 25, No. 1, 2025, “*Navigating Stakeholder Capitalism: Exploring Holistic Business Conduct and Guiding Principles*”
- Sustainability Accounting, Management and Policy Journal Special Issue, Vol. 14 No. 2, 2023, “*Driving impact through responsible investing and finance*”
- Journal of International Education in Business Special Issue: Vol. 15 No. 1, 2022, “*Best Sustainability Teaching Practices*”
- Corporate Governance Special Issue: Vol. 21, No. 2, 2021, “*Business in Society: Measuring Impact and Creating Change*”
- Corporate Governance Special Issue: Vol. 14, No. 5, 2014, “*Corporate Governance, Sustainability and Finance*”
- Business & Professional Ethics Journal Vol. 33, No. 4, 2014, “*ABIS Doctoral Summer School 2013*”
- Journal of Management Development Special Issue: Vol. 31, No. 3, 2012, “*Experiential learning and management education*”
- Business & Professional Ethics Journal Special Issue: Vol. 31, No. 2, 2012, “*EABIS Decennial*”
- Corporate Governance Special Issue: Vol. 12, No. 4, 2012, “*A new era of development: the changing role and responsibility of business in developing countries*”
- Journal of Management Development Special Issue: Vol. 30, No. 7-8, 2011, “*Practical Wisdom*”
- Journal of Management Development Special Issue: Vol. 30, No. 10, 2011, “*Integrating Sustainability in Business Models*”
- Corporate Governance Journal Special Issue: Vol. 11, No. 4, 2011, “*Corporate Responsibility and Emerging Markets*”
- Corporate Governance Journal Special Issue: Vol. 11, No. 5, 2011, “*The Future of Corporate Governance*”
- *Corporate social responsibility education in Europe: Trends and comparisons*, Orlitzky M. & Moon J., Journal of Management & Organization (2011) 17: 583-603
- Journal of Management Development Special Issue: Vol. 29, No. 7-8, 2010 “*Practical Wisdom in Management*”
- Corporate Governance Journal Special Issue: Vol. 10, No. 4, 2010 “*CR and Governance: The Responsible Corporation in a Global Economy*”
- Journal of Business Ethics Education Special Issue: Volume 5, 2008 “*Mainstreaming Corporate Responsibility*”
- Corporate Governance Journal Special Issue: Vol. 9, Issue 4, 2009 “*Corporate responsibility and sustainability: leadership and organizational challenge*”

- Corporate Governance Journal Special Issue: Vol. 8, Issue 4, 2008: “*Business in society and the emerging global governance paradigm*”
- Corporate Governance Journal Special Issue: Vol. 7, Issue 4, 2007: “*Corporate Responsibility and Strategic Management*”
- Journal of Business Ethics Special Issue: Vol. 67, No. 3, 2006: “*Corporate Responsibility & small and medium-sized enterprises*”
- Corporate Governance Journal Special Issue: Vol. 6, Issue 4, 2006: “*Corporate Responsibility and Competitiveness*”
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